

STUDY OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE SUBSTANCES IN THE CONTENT OF CHAMOMILE BY THE METHOD OF MASS SPECTROSCOPY

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Abstract: An experimental study was made of the method of using supercritical technologies to obtain chamomile plant extracts. A schematic diagram of an experimental setup for the study of supercritical extraction of biologically active substances from chamomile is presented. The results of a study of high-performance liquid chromatography with tandem mass-spectrometric detection for the identification of extracted biologically active substances and their mass yield are presented.

Key words: aralosides; biologically active substances; high performance liquid chromatography; ginsenosides; mass spectrometry; saponins; supercritical extraction; flavonoids.

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, medicinal plants are used as a source of necessary phytochemical and biologically active substances: flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, amino acids, pigments, fatty acids, etc. [1]. Many phytochemicals are used as food additives, components in pharmaceuticals and cosmetics. The use of supercritical technologies for the production of plant extracts dates back to the late 1970s [2]. Compared to similar extraction methods, supercritical extraction is carried out at low temperatures, which avoids the degradation of thermolabile biologically active substances, and in the absence of toxic solvents, while maintaining the biological activity of the target components. The use of inexpensive, environmentally friendly, and nontoxic solvents in supercritical extraction makes it possible to use the resulting extracts in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries [3–14]. At the same time, solvents in the supercritical state have a better dissolving ability due to the high diffusion coefficient and the ability of the supercritical solvent to penetrate into the plant cell [15].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The object of research is the flowers of the Uzbek chamomile. The method of maceration was taken as a method for obtaining an extract, standardization was

carried out using a chemical method. The composition of the extract was studied by mass spectrometry (CHROMATOEK-CRYSTAL 5000)

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Based on the results of analytical studies, the mass yield of aralosides A and C obtained by supercritical extraction and liquid extraction is presented. The composition of the Aralia extract corresponds to the data presented in [15]. During chromatography, the retention time of aralosides was 3.9; 4; 4.6 and 4.8 min for araloside A and its isomers; 3.7 min for araloside C and its isomer. Using the developed technique of high-performance liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry (chromatoek-crystal 5000), it was found that the content of aralosides is 1.5 times higher in the extract obtained by supercritical extraction than by liquid extraction. The composition of the chamomile extract corresponds to the data presented in the literature [15]. When chromatographed, the retention time of ginsenosides was 0.8; 2.1; 3.1; 3.4; 3.6; 4.5; 4.7; 5.8; 6.4; 6.9 and 7.3 min. The mass yield of ginsenosides in extracts by supercritical extraction was more than 1.2 times higher than the mass yield by liquid extraction. Based on the results of Chromatoek-Crystal 5000, c, the mass yield of saponins obtained by liquid extraction is shown. Chromatography showed a retention time of 38 minutes for protodiscin in the liquid extraction extract. Also, when analyzing the extract, a glycosidic residue of solanine was found.

CONCLUSIONS

These results allow us to assert the feasibility of using supercritical technologies to extract biologically active substances from chamomile. A mixture of carbon dioxide, ethyl alcohol and water was used as an extractant. The supercritical extraction process is a promising method for extracting aralosides from chamomile. The use of supercritical technologies makes it possible to extract aglycone and the glycosidic residue of solanine from tribulus. In addition, the obtained extracts can be used as food additives and components for pharmaceutical preparations.

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